

pound against the different species is compound **8a**, since it inhibits the growth of the different tested organism specially *C. albican* (zone of inhibition 9 mm). Meanwhile its inhibitory effects on the other organisms are approximately similar.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a UNICAM Sp-1200 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian spectrometer (60 MHz) with TMS as internal standard. Elemental analyses were performed at Micronalytical Center, Cairo University.

Hydrolysis of 1 to 2: Compound **1** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in concentrated H_2SO_4 (30 ml) and heated on a steam-bath for 3 h. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and poured over crushed ice (100 g) and the resulting solid was dried (76%), m.p. 190° (EtOH); ν_{max} 1 660 (C=O), 3 400 (NH_2) $1\ 100\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (-S-); δ 2.5-2.7 (6H, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 6.3 (2H, br, NH_2), 3.5 (s, SH), 7.1-7.4 (1H, ArH).

Oxidation of 2 to 3: To a solution of **2** (0.01 mol) in benzene (30 ml) was added a solution of iodine (0.02 mol) in benzene (10 ml) and the solution was refluxed for 5 h. Then excess iodine was destroyed with a saturated solution of potassium hydroxide and the resulting solid was isolated (59%), m.p. 239° (EtOH); ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), $1\ 100\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (-S-); δ 9.6 (1H, br, NH), 2.3-2.6 (6H, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.4-7.9 (1H, m, ArH).

Conversion of 1 to 4: Compound **1** (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of sodium hypochlorite (20 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. Ammonium hydroxide (50 ml) was then added to it and the mixture was stirred for additional 1 h at room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with water, (62%), m.p. 145° (EtOH); ν_{max} 3 300 (NH_2), 2 230 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), $1\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=N), δ 2.4-2.7 (6H, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 6.1 (2H, br, NH_2), 7.2-8.0 (1H, ArH).

Oxidation of 4 to 5: To a solution of **4** (0.01 mol) in acetone (20 ml) was added a solution of potassium permanganate (0.02 mol) in water (60 ml) portionwise and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for

12 h. The excess permanganate was then destroyed with sulphur dioxide and the solution filtered to remove the precipitated manganese dioxide. The aqueous solution was made strongly alkaline with NaOH pellets (3 g) and extracted with chloroform (3×20 ml). Evaporation of the dried (Na_2SO_4) chloroform extract gave the product (47%), m.p. 168° (EtOH); ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 2 250 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1 350, 1 150 (SO_2); δ 7.2-8.0 (1H, ArH), 6.3 (2H, br, NH_2).

Oxidation of pyridinethiol 1 with Cl_2/HCl . Formation of 6: To a solution of **1** (0.01 mol) in concentrated HCl (20 ml), Cl_2 gas was bubbled at 0° . After 1 h the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and dried.

Reaction of 1 and/or 6 with aroylhydrazines. Formation of 7a, b: A mixture of **1** and/or **6** (0.01 mol), and aroylhydrazines, namely, benzoyl- and 4-chlorobenzoyl hydrazine (0.01 mol) in n-butanol (60 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The solid that separated after cooling was crystallised from the proper solvent to give the products: **7a** (64%), m.p. 239° (EtOH); ν_{max} 1 580 (C=N), 2 230 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$); δ 2.3-2.6 (6H, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.4-8.1 (6H, m, ArH); **7b** (66%), m.p. 260° (EtOH); ν_{max} 1 560 (C=N), 2 230 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$); δ 2.4-2.8 (6H, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.6-8.2 (5H, ArH).

Reaction of 1 with aroylisothiocyanate. Formation of 8a, b: To a solution of ammonium thiocyanate (0.01 mol) in acetone (30 ml), equimolar aroyl chloride (namely, benzoyl chloride and 4-chlorobenzoyl chloride) was added dropwise with shaking. After heating the mixture on a steam-bath for 1 h, equimolar quantity of **1** was added and refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue treated with ice-cold water. The solid that separated was filtered, dried and crystallised: **8a** (73%), m.p. 115° (MeOH); ν_{max} 3 350-3 300 (OH, NH), 2 200 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1 680 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N), $1\ 540\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=S); δ 2.4-2.6 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 9.3 (1H, br, NH), 7.1-7.6 (6H, m, ArH); **8b** (77%), m.p. 185° (MeOH); ν_{max} 3 300-3 200 (OH, NH), 2 230 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1 700 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N), $1\ 520\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=S); δ 2.2-2.5 (6H, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 9.5 (1H, br, NH), 7.3-7.8 (5H, m, ArH).

Conversion of 6 to 1: A mixture of **6** (0.01 mol)

and thiourea (0.01 mol) in n-butanol was refluxed for 3 h. The solid produced was filtered and dried to give **1**.

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